

DISTANCE LEARNING MODALITIES IN THE NEW NORMAL

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ABSTRACT

In today's crisis due to COVID 19 pandemic, educators go along with the paradigm shift in education, hence, learners faced several challenges as well. Thus, in this study, the researchers would like to find out the perception and challenges met by the students in the higher learning institution relative to the adaptation of Distance Learning modalities. Descriptive research design was employed where sixteen programs were the source of data with 1,747 total sample respondents. Data were collected through the use of online forms and distributed through emails, and other social media platforms. The survey found out that both the online and modular mode of learning contributed to family savings. Whereas, the challenges met by the students in the online mode were the difficulty in understanding the lessons and disruptions in attending classes such as household chores, unstable internet connections and too many activities were required by the teachers. Notably, what these students identified were the challenges related to learning materials content, household distractions and independent learning. Therefore, it is suggested that the teachers should enhance the delivery of lessons and likewise develop a course design by adopting the interactive learning in online and modular approach. Also, intensifying the technological support by the higher learning institutions to both teachers and students shall be propounded.

Keywords: Education, distance learning, modalities, online survey, Philippines